

Optimizing Logistics Operations: Identifying and Mitigating Risks through FMEA and Poka Yoke

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ABSTRACT: The logistics industry plays a crucial role in facilitating the smooth distribution of goods both nationally and internationally. With the growth of the transportation and warehousing sector contributing significantly to Indonesia's GDP, logistics companies are increasingly vital in supporting trade activities. However, logistics companies face significant challenges, especially when shipping high-risk goods such as hazardous chemicals, which require careful handling due to their potential hazards to human health, safety, and the environment. In addition, maintaining service quality is essential to ensure consumer satisfaction, as delays, errors in documentation, and other issues can lead to dissatisfaction. PT XYZ, a logistics company in Indonesia, has encountered operational issues leading to delays in shipments, caused by factors such as bad weather, inconsistent schedules, and incomplete or inaccurate shipping documents. This study applies risk management techniques, specifically Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) and Poka Yoke, to identify, assess, and mitigate risks in PT XYZ's shipping operations. 15 risks are obtained with the most critical risk is inaccurate information about the goods being shipped, resulting in delays and financial losses. The Risk Priority Number (RPN) for this risk was calculated as 252, indicating a high severity and frequency of occurrence. To mitigate this risk, the study recommends implementing a Smart Logistic Checker system, which integrates automatic technologies such as barcode scanning, digital weighing, dimension measurement, and label printing, with automatic validation to ensure that the information matches the physical condition of the goods. This approach aims to reduce errors, enhance operational efficiency, and prevent failure.

KEYWORDS: FMEA, Goods Shipment, Poka Yoke, Risk Management, Shipping Delay

INTRODUCTION

The logistics industry is one of the industries that plays an important role in supporting the smooth distribution of goods both nationally and internationally. Based on data from the Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS), the transportation and warehousing sector experienced significant growth of 9.56% (year-on-year) in the second quarter of 2024 and contributed 6.24% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2024). This data shows the importance of this sector in the Indonesian economy, especially in supporting domestic and foreign trade activities. Logistics companies provide services that can organize the shipping process of goods with various modes of transportation. This company helps in storing and transporting resources such as equipment, food and materials to the desired destination (Archetti & Peirano, 2020).

Logistics companies face major challenges, especially in shipping high-risk goods such as hazardous chemicals used in various industrial sectors such as manufacturing, agriculture, and health (Naidu et al., 2021). These hazardous chemicals must be handled carefully because they can pose serious dangers to the health and safety of humans, the environment, and other living things (Ostad-Ali-Askari, 2022). In addition, logistics companies must ensure the quality of services provided to consumers in order to increase consumer satisfaction. This is because the gap between consumer perceptions and expectations can lead to consumer dissatisfaction, such as late delivery, lack of understanding of documents, document errors, product damage, product loss, and high costs for consumers (Limoubpratum et al., 2020).

PT XYZ is one of the logistics companies in Indonesia. This company provides shipping services via land, sea, and air. In its operational activities, PT XYZ has problems that can disrupt the shipping process, namely delays in shipping caused by several factors such as bad weather, inconsistencies in shipping schedules, incomplete shipping documents, inconsistencies in goods data, and so on. The following is data on shipment delays in January-March 2024:

Table 1. Shipment Delays from January - March 2024

Month	Total Shipment	Shipment Delay
January	24	6
February	27	19
March	29	24
Total	80	49

Based on these problems, it is important to carry out risk management to identify and mitigate various risks that can harm the company. The risk management method used in this study is Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) and Poka Yoke. With these methods, it is expected to help companies identify the risks they have along with their causes and impacts on the company, know the priority order of risk improvement. In addition, this study also provides risk mitigation suggestions for improvement based on Poka Yoke concept approach so that the company's operational activities can be more effective, efficient, and can prevent failure from occurring.

METHOD

Risk Management

Risk management is a comprehensive approach to addressing all events that can result in losses. The risk management process helps individuals or companies understand the potential losses that may occur and ensures that the organizations delivers safe services (Abrudan & Baru, 2020). Risk management is also a field of science that teaches an organization to be able to recognize and handle various problems systematically involving a series of policies and procedures to manage, monitor, and control the risks faced. The purpose of implementing risk management is to protect an organization or company from significant risks that can interfere with the achievement of the goals of the organization or company. This includes ensuring that all risks have been identified, assessed, and action plans have been prepared to reduce the impact and likelihood of these risks occurring (Gurtu & Johny, 2021). According to (ISO, 2018), the purpose of risk management is to create and protect value. Risk management improves performance, drives innovation, and supports the achievement of goals. In order for risk management to run effectively, efficiently, and consistently, ISO 31000 directs organizations or companies to refer to three pillars, namely principles, frameworks, and processes (Rampini et al., 2019). The principles, framework and processes of risk management according to ISO 31000:2018 in the Risk Management Guidelines are as follows (ISO, 2018):

Figure 1. The Principles, Framework, and Processes of Risk Management According to ISO 3100:2018

Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA)

Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) is a systematic approach that focuses on identifying, evaluating, and mitigating the chances of failure in a process or product (Minguito & Banluta, 2023). Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) is also a method to determine the ranking of causes of failure of a process so that improvement priorities can be obtained (Huang et al., 2020). In

addition, Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) can also be described as a systematic group of activities to recognize and evaluate the potential for failure of a product or process and its impacts, identify actions that can eliminate or reduce the possibility of potential failure, and the process of defining what a design or process must do to satisfy customers. (Ford Motor Company, 2011).

Poka Yoke

Poka Yoke comes from the Japanese word "Poka" which means mistake and "Yokeru" which means avoid, so it can be interpreted as mistake proofing or error proofing or error prevention. The Poka Yoke method was first introduced by a Toyota Motor Corporation engineer named Shigeo Shingo in 1961. Poka Yoka is defined as a concept for designing a system or product in such a way that failure cannot occur or if failure occurs, it can be immediately detected and can be repaired immediately (Trojanowska et al., 2023). Poka yoke is intended to eliminate product defects or prevent machine operators from making mistakes by detecting and analyzing the root cause (Ortiz Porras et al., 2023).

Research Object

The object of this research is all risks associated with the shipment process at PT XYZ.

Research Subject

The subjects of this research were experts in the field of shipment at PT XYZ, consisting of supervisors, IHC claritiant coordinators, and IHC claritiant staff.

Data Collection Method

This research uses various data collection methods, namely interviews, observations, and filling out questionnaires. Interviews were conducted with PT XYZ experts to determine business processes, factors that can cause risks, risk events, and the impact of these risks. Observations were made on all processes related to the shipment to obtain actual information about the process. Questionnaires were used to determine the severity, frequency, and detection required in determining the Risk Priority Number (RPN) value for FMEA method.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA)

In the FMEA method, there are several steps that must be taken, namely identifying the risks that can occur in the process of shipping accompanied by identifying the causes of the risk and the impact of the risk on the company. Then, weighting the severity, occurrence, and detection of each risk that has been identified. Next, calculate the risk priority number by multiplying the severity, occurrence, and detection weights that have been given. The results of the risk priority number (RPN) will be sorted from the largest to the smallest to determine the priority of the risk that will be improved. The results of the FMEA method are as follows.

Risk Identification

In this section, risk identification is carried out to determine the risks that can arise from operational activities of shipping along with their causes and impacts on the company. The following are the results of the risk identification:

Table 2. Risk Identification

No	Risk	Cause of Risk	Effect of Risk
1	Shipment price mismatch.	Mismatch between estimated cost and actual shipping cost.	Financial loss for the company and customer.
2	Price does not match the tender.	Calculation differences or pricing policy by third parties.	Customer dissatisfaction, reduced trust.
3	Unstable price fluctuations.	Market fluctuations or changes in service provider policies.	Financial loss and service price instability.
4	Excalating shipping costs.	Unexpected tariff changes or new pricing policies.	Increased shipping costs and impact on profit margin.

5	Incorrect communication of hazardous chemical information.	Errors in internal communication.	Risk of accidents, regulatory violations.
6	Information about the goods to be shipped is inaccurate.	Lack of coordination between the shipping teams, carelessness in checking	Delayed distribution of goods, financial losses.
7	Miscommunication between quality assurance and system or vessel.	Unclear procedures and poor coordination.	Compromised quality of goods shipped, accidents.
8	Errors in scheduling hazardous chemical shipments.	Irregularities in logistics planning.	Delayed hazardous chemical shipments, safety risks.
9	Vessel does not meet safety standards for hazardous chemical transport.	Non-compliance between vessel and hazardous materials transport regulations.	Risk of accidents, pollution, and legal violations.
10	Incomplete shipping document.	Oversight in document verification or errors in document filling.	Shipping delays and customs or legal issues.
11	Errors in labeling and symbol application for hazardous chemicals	Mistakes in labeling procedures or poor supervision.	Safety violations, risk of accidents on site.
12	Contamination of hazardous chemicals with other material.	Unsafe packaging or accidental mixing.	Chemical damage, risk of fire or pollution.
13	Container damage.	Use of old or damaged containers.	Damage to goods and contamination of hazardous.
14	Shipment delays.	Issues with transport mode or planning errors.	Decreased customer satisfaction and financial loss.
15	Damage to goods	Improper shipping or poor handling of goods.	Loss of goods, financial loss, and customer trust issues.

Risk Priority Number (RPN) Calculation

After identifying the risk along with its causes and impacts, the next step is to assign severity, occurrence, and detection weights. Then calculate the risk priority number (RPN) by multiplying the severity, occurrence, and detection weights. The following are the results of the risk priority number (RPN) calculation:

Table 3. Risk Priority Number (RPN) Calculation

No	Risk	Severity	Occurrence	Detection	RPN
1	Shipment price mismatch.	6	5	4	120
2	Price does not match the tender.	6	4	4	96
3	Unstable price fluctuations.	6	3	4	72
4	Exalating shipping costs.	6	3	3	54
5	Incorrect communication of hazardous chemical information.	9	2	5	90
6	Information about the goods to be shipped is inaccurate.	9	7	4	252

7	Miscommunication between quality assurance and system or vessel.	9	2	5	90
8	Errors in scheduling hazardous chemical shipments.	8	2	3	48
9	Vessel does not meet safety standards for hazardous chemical transport.	9	7	3	189
10	Incomplete shipping document.	8	3	2	48
11	Errors in labeling and symbol application for hazardous chemicals	8	4	3	96
12	Contamination of hazardous chemicals with other material.	9	3	4	108
13	Container damage.	7	5	5	175
14	Shipment delays.	9	5	4	180
15	Damage to goods	8	6	3	144

Table 4. Risk Priority Number Ranking

No	Risk	Severity	Occurrence	Detection	RPN
1	Information about the goods to be shipped is inaccurate.	9	7	4	252
2	Vessel does not meet safety standards for hazardous chemical transport.	9	7	3	189
3	Shipment delays.	9	5	4	180
4	Container damage.	7	5	5	175
5	Damage to goods	8	6	3	144
6	Shipment price mismatch.	6	5	4	120
7	Contamination of hazardous chemicals with other material.	9	3	4	108
8	Price does not match the tender.	6	4	4	96
9	Errors in labeling and symbol application for hazardous chemicals	8	4	3	96
10	Incorrect communication of hazardous chemical information.	9	2	5	90
11	Miscommunication between quality assurance and system or vessel.	9	2	5	90
12	Unstable price fluctuations.	6	3	4	72
13	Exalating shipping costs.	6	3	3	54
14	Errors in scheduling hazardous chemical shipments.	8	2	3	48
15	Incomplete shipping document.	8	3	2	48

Based on the calculation results of the Risk Priority Number (RPN) that has been carried out, the highest RPN value is 252, which is the risk of information about the goods to be shipped is inaccurate. This risk has a severity level of 9, which means that incorrect information regarding the goods to be sent is very critical because it can lead to incorrect handling methods, violations of applicable regulations, and potentially causing accidents in handling them. This risk has a frequency of occurrence of 7, which

means that this risk occurs quite often. The detection capability for this risk is 4, which means that it is quite difficult to detect. This risk occurs due to a lack of coordination between the shipping team and the carelessness of workers in checking goods. The impact of this risk is late delivery because workers will check and re-adjust information about goods and can cause financial losses for both the company and consumers. This will also affect the quality of the company's services, which can cause trust issues for consumers and consumer dissatisfaction.

Poka Yoke

After identifying the risks and calculating the risk priority order using the FMEA method, a risk mitigation design is then carried out to improve the company's operational activities. This risk mitigation design uses the Poka Yoke concept to prevent failure or if the failure occurs, it can be detected immediately. Of the 15 identified risks, one main risk with the highest RPN value was selected to carry out the mitigation design. The priority risk is that the information about the goods to be shipped is inaccurate. The recommended risk mitigation to reduce the main risk is to use a smart logistic checker system (Chung, 2021). Smart logistic checker is an automatic technology-based tool that combines the functions of a barcode scanner, digital scales, barcode label printing, and automatic validation to ensure that the information on the goods to be ship matches their physical condition. The main components of this tool are as follows:

1. Digital Scales

Weigh goods automatically with high accuracy.

Automatic Dimension Camera

Measure the length, width, and height of goods automatically.

3. Automatic Barcode Label Printer

Prints barcode labels that contain goods data such as sender's name, destination address, recipient's name, weight and dimensions of goods, type of goods, location of goods sorting, shipping media, etc. In addition, this tool will also print special labels according to the type of goods such as flammable, explosive, toxic, etc.

4. Indicator Screen and Alarm

Provides visual and audible notifications if there is data inputted by the shipping worker that is incomplete or there is an error.

Data regarding the goods information, will be sent to the company's logistics management system so that it can be accessed by the sender, shipping worker, and recipient. The following is the flow of goods delivery by implementing a smart logistics checker:

Figure 2. Goods Delivery Process by Implementing Smart Logistic Checker

The explanation of the flowchart above is as follows:

1. Goods from the sender are received at the logistics center.

2. The delivery worker moves the goods to the smart logistics checker.
3. The delivery worker performs manual input on the smart logistics checker regarding the name of the delivery, name of the recipient, name of the goods, type of goods, delivery address, delivery media, special treatment of goods, and so on. The smart logistics checker weighs the goods with a digital scale and measures the dimensions of the goods such as length, width, and height of the goods with an automatic dimension measuring camera.
4. The smart logistics checker prints a barcode label containing data on the goods and a special label if the goods require special handling because they are included in the type of dangerous goods. Then, the delivery worker attaches the label to the goods to be sent.
5. The goods data will be sent to the company's logistics management system so that it can be accessed by the sender, delivery worker, and recipient. The system will automatically group the goods according to the appropriate sorting area based on the handling method, delivery destination, and delivery media.
6. The goods are moved to the sorting area using a conveyor. The scanner on the conveyor will scan the label on the goods to find out the location of the appropriate sorting area. Then, the goods will go to the right sorting area location.
7. The scanner in the sorting area will scan the label on the goods to validate whether the goods are indeed included in the sorting area. If the data is valid, the goods will be placed in that area. However, if the data is invalid, the machine will sound an alarm and the indicator light will come on to notify the worker that the goods are in the wrong sorting area, so that the worker can move the goods to the right sorting area.
8. Goods are sent with proper handling and information about the goods to be sent is accurate.
9. Goods are received by the recipient in good condition with the right quantity.

By implementing a smart logistic checker tool, logistics companies can mitigate the risk of inaccurate information regarding goods for shipment. This ensures that operational processes are carried out effectively and efficiently, leading to increased productivity and enhancing the company's competitiveness in the market (Abrudan et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that has been carried out regarding the risks that occur in operational activities for shipping goods, the following conclusions were obtained:

1. Based on the results of the risk identification that has been carried out, 15 risks were obtained in operational activities in the process of shipping goods. Priority risks were obtained with the results of the Risk Priority Number (RPN) of 252, namely the risk of information about the goods to be shipped is inaccurate. This risk is caused by the lack of coordination between the shipping teams and the carelessness in checking. This risk has an impact on delayed distribution of goods and financial losses.
2. Risk mitigation that can be applied to prevent the occurrence of priority risks is by designing risk mitigation to prevent failure with the poka yoke concept, namely a smart logistic checker. Smart logistic checker is an automatic technology-based tool that combines the functions of a barcode scanner, digital scales, barcode label printing, and automatic validation to ensure that the information on the goods to be ship matches their physical condition.

SUGGESTION

The suggestion that can be given is that the company can implement risk mitigation suggestion with the poka yoke concept that has been given, namely the smart logistic checker in the operational activities of shipping goods, so that the operational activities of the company can run effectively and efficiently. The company is also advised to evaluate operational risk management periodically so that the risk mitigation implemented can be relevant to the latest conditions. Suggestions for further research can examine the company's financial and strategic risks, design the risk mitigation system given in this study and implement it to the company.

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